

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING SPEAKING FOR ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS AT DAK LAK COLLEGE OF PEDAGOGY AND SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Together with the development of information technology in all aspects of teaching and learning, there exists challenge in EFL classes. In reality, the lecturers at colleges and universities often have problems in teaching speaking for students in general and for majored students in particular. This article deals with difficulties in teaching speaking for English major students and suggest some solutions to this problem. Based on the current status of teaching and learning major English at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy, and in order to improve teaching speaking for English major students effectively, there should be a great shift in both perception and action of lecturers and students to improve the quality of major English training at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy so as to adapt their English to jobs and social needs in future.

Keywords: English major students, lecturers, students.

1 INTRODUCTION

English has a great importance to be taught and learned at colleges and universities. In many EFL classes, speaking is still underestimated while reading and writing are prioritized. This is partly because these skills are weighted more in examinations. In reality, some students understand English grammar very well, and even score high marks in examinations, but their communication skills are very poor and they are often too shy to speak in front of other people. This is because they have no environment for communication in and out of the classroom. Moreover, others may not understand the value of oracy activities because they do not see real work being done as compared with other tasks. Another reason is that some students are still afraid to learn English. Most of them struggle to speak English and find it difficult to complete the intermediate course. They only learn enough English to pass examinations, when in reality, they need to be able to communicate. That's why their speaking skills are poor and the students become frustrated by this.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Difficulties of teaching speaking for English major students at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy

2.1.1 *Students just keep sitting quiet and can't say anything*

First and foremost, the topic of the lesson is sometimes both boring and unfamiliar, so it can't attract students' attention. Then, students don't have enough time to organize and develop ideas in

real time because most students are in the habit of arranging the ideas in their mind first and begin to speak out then. They find it difficult to communicate orally under the pressure of real time demand. That's why their speaking is often tripped over and not fluent.

2.1.2 Students avoid communicative activities for fear of not performing well in front of their peers

Quite a lot of students are not able to adapt when moving from high school to new learning environment - an environment that requires learners to have skills and methods of learning completely different from those in high school. In high school, students haven't been equipped with self-study methods, not paying attention to training self-study skills, especially speaking skill. To students, some of the tasks are so difficult to understand and do in limited time. That's the reason why some students just keep sitting quiet and can't say anything. Another reason is that students are afraid of not performing well in front of their peers because they find it difficult to produce chunks (phrases), ask for clarification or check their understanding.

2.1.3 Participation may be dominated by certain students in the class

To the English learning context at most colleges and universities, speaking is the skill that is emphasized in the course of study. The students are required to take the speaking course as one of compulsory sections. Although students have spent much time to improve their speaking ability, in fact, most of them are still not very confident in and sometimes get confused with their speaking. Only a few good students can do this and often actively speak and participate in activities set by lecturers because these students understand and grasp the problem quite quickly. The interaction between these students and their lecturer becomes easier than ever. For these students, speaking English appears to be completely effortless.

Meanwhile, the others find it difficult to join in. They often have dependence and laziness during class. The more they depend, the less they speak. It discourages lecturers a lot. Thus, it is important for lecturers to understand what the solutions to the problem are and what students need to enable better speaking performances.

2.1.4 Students may be inhibited by fear of making language mistakes

That students may be inhibited by fear of making language mistakes becomes common in most speaking classes at colleges and universities. The oral fluency of learners greatly depends on their grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence and strategic competence. How can lecturers help their students get out of this bad habit? For speaking, it is important first to give competence and then performance.

2.1.5 Students don't seem to understand what to do in speaking activities

Lecturers often get frustrated because some students do not attempt to speak at all. This is partly because students don't seem to understand what to do in speaking activities. When the lecturer wants his/her students to be active, they prefer to be passive. This is a universal problem. How to make the unmotivated or semi-motivated students to speak and how to motivate lazy students?

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Suggested solutions to teaching speaking for English major students at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy

3.1.1 *Topics should be personalised and made interesting for the students*

One of the most important factors that attracts students at the beginning of the lesson is *the topic*. In order to attract students' attention right at the beginning of the lesson, the topic needs to be interesting, familiar and personalized. The lecturers can also change or adapt the topic in the book if needed. Besides, to help students confident, give them time to think and plan what they are going to say.

3.1.2 *Activity difficulty should be adapted/ changed to the level of the class*

Another factor that affects the class atmosphere is *the activity difficulty*. Be sure the speaking activities are not too hard for students. Instructions, activities and contexts, should all be clear and understood enough. Elicit suitable vocabulary and phrases for the students, so they can grasp easily. The lecturer should also help students with knowledge of grammar system, appropriate language, suitable exchange patterns, phonology, topic and awareness of what the listener knows and is interested in. One more important thing is that speaking should be intergrated to other skills. To do these, students will be able to speak out fluently, produce chunks, ask for clarification or check their understanding.

3.1.3 *Pair work and group work should be used to provide an environment for good interaction*

The lecturers should encourage their students to speak. Try moving students into different groups/ pairs to keep things fresh and interesting. Regularly change these options, including going outside every now and then. Doing this appeals to different student types and allow them time to work with their peer as well. It's also important for the lecturer to provide useful corrective feedback to the students.

3.1.4 *Chances for peer-correction and self- correction should be given*

The lecturers should try to speak less and get their students to speak more. Help to create a good atmosphere in the class - an atmosphere where students are unafraid and realistic about their accuracy targets. While it is good to aim for 100% accuracy when you are practising specific language items, it certainly isn't good when you are doing a more communicative task in which the students will need to use a very wide range of language elements. Here are some ways of making the unmotivated or semi-motivated students to speak:

- + give very clear instructions, provide an example and allow students to ask any questions they may have before getting started.
- + attract students by using video, postcards, songs, realia or instruments...
- + organize some healthy competitions through grammar games, whiteboard games, word games...
- + give students a chance to work with other students: in pairs, in small groups and in open class.
- + give feedback skillfully.

Below are the lecturer's roles during a speaking lesson:

Role(s)	What to do?
<i>Organizer</i>	Getting students engaged and setting up activities.
<i>Prompter</i>	Providing students with reasons to speak.
<i>Participant</i>	Encouraging real communication by taking part in speaking activities.
<i>Assessor</i>	Observing students in order to provide them with a mark for their performances.
<i>Feedback provider</i>	Giving students details about what they are getting right and wrong, so they can improve their performances.
<i>Resource</i>	Helping students with their language needs, so they can communicate better and more accurately.

In this way, I do believe that the lecturer will help students with their language needs and not discourage them.

3.1.5 Lecturers should move from controlled to freer activity types when their students are ready

Controlled speaking activities normally have a specific language focus i.e. intensive practice of one or more language structures/ items with an emphasis on getting the right form.

Freer speaking activities can be used to provide meaningful practice of one, or a small number of language structures/items, with an emphasis on how and when to use the structure(s) to get meaning across. They can also be used for fluency practice of language skills in general.

Below are some common forms of controlled and freer speaking activities:

<i>Controlled speaking activities</i>	Drilling
	Substitutions
	Expansions
	Disappearing texts
	Transformations
<i>Freer speaking activities</i>	Role-plays
	Interviews/Questionnaires/Surveys
	Presentations
	Drama
	Discussions
	Meetings
	Storytelling/Anecdotes/Jokes
Project work	

	Problem - solving activities
	Ranking activities
	Information gap activities
	“Talk for a minute” type activities
	Creating dialogues

The lecturers should set up speaking activities carefully and use a combination of visual elements (e.g. on the board) and verbal instructions as verbal instructions alone can be difficult to understand/hear. Keep things simple, so you don't confuse the students. Plan the actual wording of your instructions in advance, so you can get across your instructions with the minimum number of words and the clearest way:

- + make sure the context for the task is clear and understood.
- + make sure there is a clear reason for the students to speak.

Besides, the lecturers should anticipate possible problems and provide support before and during the speaking activity...

4 CONCLUSION

From what the author mentioned and presented above, the status of teaching speaking for English major students at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy is still limited. This requires a drastic change and takes drastic measures from both lecturers and learners to improve the quality of major English training at Dak Lak College of Pedagogy so as to adapt their English to jobs and social needs in future.

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